

Supplementary Material: gPC-based robustness analysis of neural systems through probabilistic recurrence metrics

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Summary of the presented material

This document contains Supplementary Material about our novel methodology for gPC-based robustness analysis of neural systems through probabilistic recurrence metrics.

For demonstration purposes, as our uncertain systems $\dot{\mathbf{x}} = f(\mathbf{x}, Z)$ under study, we consider the HR model given by equation (2.2) in the Main Text, with the membrane potential $y(t) = x_1(t) = \mathbf{x}_1(t; Z)$ as the output signal of interest for the analysis, and the JR model given by equation (2.3) in the Main Text, with the EEG-like signal $y(t) = x_2(t) - x_3(t) = \mathbf{x}_2(t; Z) - \mathbf{x}_3(t; Z)$ as the output of interest.

In Section S1, we consider different deterministic realisations of neural systems and we compare deterministic realisations with mean neural signals obtained in a probabilistic setting.

In particular, for the HR model, Figure S1 shows the deterministic realisation in the square-wave bursting regime, and the corresponding recurrence plot, associated with the nominal system configuration for the case study in Figure 3 of the Main Text.

For the JR model, Figure S2 shows examples of deterministic realisations that are representative of different dynamical regimes, along with the corresponding recurrence plots.

Then, considering the HR model as a case study, we provide additional insight into the fundamental difference between a deterministic framework and a probabilistic framework when assessing regime preservation. Particularly, in Figure S3 we show that, when analysing models subject to parametric uncertainty, considering a *deterministic* model realisation associated with average system parameters is insufficiently informative to faithfully allow for estimating regime preservation, in contrast to employing the mean state trajectory and the corresponding output signal. In fact, given two deterministic realisations corresponding to parameter values Z_1 and Z_2 , the qualitative behaviour of the deterministic realisation corresponding to the average parameter value $\frac{Z_1+Z_2}{2}$ is not representative of the qualitative behaviour of the two original realisations, and hence cannot provide any meaningful information about their dynamical regime.

Figure S4 further provides intuition and a numerical demonstration to explain why assessing regime preservation under probabilistic parametric uncertainty through the mean output signal is extremely challenging for the chaotic regime, due to the extreme sensitivity to parameter variations that characterises trajectories in this regime.

In Section S2, we present unsuccessful attempts at using existing metrics and standard norms to assess regime preservation in the presence of probabilistic parametric uncertainty.

First, Figure S5 shows that, when studying mean signals, neuroscientific metrics usually adopted for deterministic signals (such as the inter-spike interval and the spike count) are not adequate.

Then, motivated by techniques from image processing, we consider the matrices associated with recurrence plots and compute several widely-used image similarity or image distance metrics (such as maximum value, average value, standard deviation and root-mean-square of all entries, spectral norm, and Frobenius norm); also these metrics cannot reliably distinguish between deterministic realisations pertaining to different regimes, as shown in Figure S6, or reliably detect loss of probabilistic robustness for increasing parametric uncertainty levels, as shown in Figure S7.

Next, for each of the different regimes, we consider pairs of two matrices: one corresponding to a recurrence plot with a clearly recognisable recurrence pattern (*i.e.*, with a small uncertainty level), taken as the reference or ground truth, and the other corresponding to recurrence plots with increasing parametric uncertainty. We interpret the matrices as describing probability mass functions and, for each pair, we compute Wasserstein distance, mutual information, and Jaccard index. Figure S8 shows that also these metrics cannot reliably detect loss of probabilistic robustness.

Finally, by considering the mean output signals as time-series, we compute their power spectral densities for increasing uncertainty levels and attempt to detect loss of probabilistic robustness through significant changes in distinctive frequency components; this is also unsuccessful, as shown in Figure S9.

The presented numerical examples clearly demonstrate the inability of all the described metrics and indices to faithfully identify regime preservation, thereby strongly motivating the need for the novel methodology proposed in our work, based on blob counting.

In Section S3, we provide details on the automated blob counting procedure for recurrence plots introduced in Section 2 (d) ii of the Main Text.

In particular, Figure S10 shows the procedure to select the value of \mathfrak{B} , the minimum acceptable blob size (in terms of number of pixels).

Figure S11 shows a case of inconclusive blob count, resulting in $\mathfrak{C}^* = \text{NaN}$, when no persistent recurrence pattern is detected above the threshold \mathfrak{P} set as the minimum acceptable persistence.

Finally, Figure S12 provides an example case in which two completely different blob counts are obtained for a nominal deterministic realisation and for the mean output signal computed when the nominal parameter values are affected by a small uncertainty, even though the two recurrence plots are visually similar.

In Section S4, we further elaborate on the procedure to construct PRP plots.

Figure S13 numerically demonstrates the suitability of the criterion, described in Section 2 (d) iii of the Main Text, that detects loss of probabilistic robustness through a $\pm 50\%$ variation in the blob count.

For two-dimensional parametric uncertainty, Figure S14 provides a detailed visual description of the algorithm to compute PRP plots with the LE approach, introduced in Section 2 (e) of the Main Text.

Finally, to further demonstrate the usefulness of the proposed methodology for PRA, Section S5 enriches the results discussed in Section 3 of the Main Text by providing more insight through additional PRP plots, for both the HR model and JR model, constructed with the LE and FG approaches introduced in Section 2 (e) of the Main Text.

Section S5.1 considers the HR model subject to uncertainty affecting parameters b and I . Figure S15 shows PRP plots obtained with the LE approach when the value of I is fixed and only b is uncertain. When both b and I are uncertain, Figure S16 shows the PRP plot obtained with the FG approach in a rectangular neighbourhood of a parameter region associated with the chaotic regime.

Section S5.2 considers the JR model subject to uncertainty affecting parameters A and B , and provides the PRP plots computed for multiple values of the parameters C and p , both with the LE approach (Figure S17) and with the FG approach (Figure S18).

Detailed descriptions are provided in the figure captions.

S1 Deterministic realisations and mean output signals

Figure S1: For the membrane potential $x_1(t)$ generated by the HR model (see equation (2.2), and the details below it, in the Main Text), with $b = 2.7$ and $I = 2.4$, in the square-wave bursting regime, we show (a) the nominal deterministic realisation (time-series) in the time window $[600,1200]$, and (b) the corresponding recurrence plot. This is the nominal case (with no uncertainty) for the case study in Figure 3 of the Main Text.

Figure S2: For the EEG-like signal $x_2(t) - x_3(t)$ generated by the JR model (see equation (2.3), and the details below it, in the Main Text) with $A = 7$ and $B = 22$, deterministic realisations in the time interval $[1.75, 2.5]$ (top) and the corresponding recurrence plots (bottom) are shown for different dynamical regimes: **(A)** alpha-wave regime, $C = 100$ and $p = 100$, yielding the highest blob count; **(B)** low-frequency wave regime, $C = 175$ and $p = 100$, yielding an intermediate blob count; **(C)** no wave regime, $C = 100$ and $p = 400$, where the signal is constant and hence, in theory, the recurrence plot should be a blue square and the resulting blob count should be zero. Here, the noticeable signal fluctuations are due to numerical noise, which often arises in practice.

Figure S3: Considering the *deterministic* realisation whose parameters are the average of multiple values in the parameter space is not informative, as demonstrated in this example for the membrane potential x_1 of the HR model. When $b = 2.97$, both current values $I = 3.52$ and $I = 2.48$ yield a deterministic realisation in the tonic spiking regime; however, when the current takes the average value $I = 3$, the corresponding deterministic realisation exhibits chaotic bursting, which is a completely unrelated regime. This aspect is captured by the *non-convex* shapes of the regime regions that one can observe in the bifurcation plot from [1] (image courtesy of Springer), reported in the middle.

Figure S4: Different points in a chaotic region in the parameter space of the HR model can yield deterministic realisations of x_1 with completely different firing patterns in the same time interval, even when the variation in the values of the system parameters is very small, resulting in a mean membrane potential $\mathbb{E}[x_1]$ with no discernible recurrence pattern, thereby leading to a zero blob count. In fact, the resulting mean signal is indistinguishable from those obtained in the quiescent regime and can be easily misclassified as belonging to that regime. We show deterministic realisations of x_1 with (a) $r = 0.0025$ and $I = 3.325$; (b) $r = 1/320$ and $I = 397/120$; (c) $r = 0.00375$ and $I = 3.325$; (d) $r = 0.0025$ and $I = 3.3$; (e) $r = 0.00375$ and $I = 3.3$; (f) $r = 0.0025$ and $I = 3.275$; (g) $r = 1/320$ and $I = 79/24$; (h) $r = 0.00375$ and $I = 3.275$. The region $[r_{\min}, r_{\max}] \times [I_{\min}, I_{\max}] = [0.0025, 0.00375] \times [3.275, 3.325]$ of the parameter space shown in (i) is a zoom of [2, Figure 1] (image courtesy of PLoS One). The mean membrane potential $\mathbb{E}[x_1]$ shown in (j) for $r \sim \mathcal{U}([0.0025, 0.00375])$ and $I \sim \mathcal{U}([3.275, 3.325])$ is computed with a gPC collocation surrogate model with maximum expansion order $M = 5$ and $S_C = 1000$ collocation samples.

S2 Preservation of dynamical regimes: Standard metrics are unsuccessful

Figure S5: (a) Standard metrics in neuroscience, such as inter-spike interval (ISI), spike count (SC), and duty cycle (burst duration/burst period), have a precise meaning and are useful to understand neurocomputational properties for a deterministic realisation, as shown for the membrane potential x_1 generated by the HR model with $I = 4$ and $b = 2.5$. (b) However, they are not suitable to study mean output signals, as shown for the HR mean membrane potential $\mathbb{E}[x_1]$ with $I = 4$ and $b \sim \mathcal{U}([2.5, 2.55])$. Even defining such metrics becomes challenging or impossible. For instance, shall one define the bursting period as starting after the maximum spike amplitude, or after some threshold $\mathbb{E}[x_1] \geq -1$ is crossed; or shall one consider all possible spikes? In both panels, red vertical lines highlight local maxima of signals, corresponding to spikes for the deterministic realisation and to “potential spikes” for the mean signal.

Figure S6: Unsuccessful attempts to distinguish between the regimes of the HR model when the Frobenius-norm, the matrix 2-norm (or spectral norm), the root-mean-square of all entries, the standard deviation of all entries, the average value of all entries, and the maximum value among all entries are employed as metrics and computed for the matrix D corresponding to the recurrence plot of the mean output signal $\mathbb{E}[x_1]$ (see Section 2 (d) i of the Main Text) in the presence of parametric uncertainty with a small uncertainty set. The recurrence plots of the mean signals exhibit clearly recognisable and distinguishable patterns, at least by visual inspection. To systematically distinguish between the different dynamical regimes in an automated fashion via a candidate metric, we would like such a metric to yield close values for recurrence plots emanating from the same regime, while exhibiting large separation between the values obtained across regimes. In practice, none of the considered metrics exhibits such behaviour definitively and for all regimes. For each of the different regimes, three stochastic realisations are considered with different parameter and uncertainty settings. Regime (A): $b = 3.1$ and $I \sim \mathcal{U}([3.6, 3.61])$; $I = 3.6$ and $b \sim \mathcal{U}([3.1, 3.11])$; $b \sim \mathcal{U}([3.1, 3.11])$ and $I \sim \mathcal{U}([3.6, 3.61])$. Regime (B): $b = 3.05$ and $I \sim \mathcal{U}([2.4, 2.41])$; $I = 2.4$ and $b \sim \mathcal{U}([3.05, 3.06])$; $b \sim \mathcal{U}([3.05, 3.06])$ and $I \sim \mathcal{U}([2.4, 2.41])$. Regime (C): $b = 2.7$ and $I \sim \mathcal{U}([2.4, 2.41])$; $I = 2.4$ and $b \sim \mathcal{U}([2.7, 2.71])$; $b \sim \mathcal{U}([2.7, 2.71])$ and $I \sim \mathcal{U}([2.4, 2.41])$. Regime (D): $b = 2.5$ and $I \sim \mathcal{U}([4.0, 4.01])$; $I = 4.0$ and $b \sim \mathcal{U}([2.5, 2.51])$; $b \sim \mathcal{U}([2.5, 2.51])$ and $I \sim \mathcal{U}([4.0, 4.01])$.

Figure S7: Unsuccessful attempts to detect loss of probabilistic robustness in the HR model when the Frobenius-norm, the matrix 2-norm (or spectral norm), the root-mean-square of all entries, the standard deviation of all entries, the average value of all entries, and the maximum value among all entries are employed as metrics and computed for the matrix D corresponding to the recurrence plot of the mean output signal $\mathbb{E}[x_1]$ (see Section 2 (d) i of the Main Text) in the presence of parametric uncertainty with increasing uncertainty levels $i = 1, \dots, 7$. To systematically detect loss of probabilistic robustness at some uncertainty level in an automated fashion via a candidate metric, we would like to observe a distinctive, abrupt relative change in the metric value (or trend) as a function of the uncertainty level, across *all* regimes under consideration. For the considered metrics, we observe that no such sharp transition in metric value is immediately discernible across all regimes; in particular, no abrupt change occurs in the differences between consecutive values for the metrics in Regime (D), plateau bursting. Moreover, for Regime (A), quiescence, the metrics are not even monotonic with the uncertainty level. Therefore, to use such metrics, additional, *ad hoc* detection criteria would need to be introduced for each regime of this specific model, which may be unsuitable for other models, such as the JR model. Thus, we conclude that analysis of probabilistic robustness based on such metrics would not be generalisable to other models. In the different regimes, the parameter and uncertainty settings are chosen as follows. Regime (A): $b = 3.2$ and I uncertain with nominal value $I^* = 3.8$ fixed as centre value and support of the uniform distribution having size $\Delta I_{\max} = 0.8$. Regime (B): $I = 2.4$ and b uncertain with nominal value $b^* = 3.0$ fixed as left end value and support of the uniform distribution having size $\Delta b_{\max} = 0.15$. Regime (C): $I = 2.6$ and b uncertain with nominal value $b^* = 2.6$ fixed as left end value and support of the uniform distribution having size $\Delta b_{\max} = 0.3$. Regime (D): $b = 2.5$ and I uncertain with nominal value $I^* = 4.0$ fixed as centre value and support of the uniform distribution having size $\Delta I_{\max} = 0.5$.

Figure S8: (a) Unsuccessful attempts to detect loss of probabilistic robustness in the HR model through Jaccard index, mutual information and Wasserstein distance, taken as metrics to quantify the difference between a recurrence plot obtained with small uncertainty level, taken as the reference (ground truth), and recurrence plots with increasing uncertainty levels $i = 1, \dots, 8$. In the different regimes, the parameter and uncertainty settings are chosen as follows. Regime (A): $b = 3.1$ and I uncertain with nominal value $I^* = 3.6$ fixed as left end value and support of the uniform distribution having size $\Delta I_{\max} = 0.4$. Regime (B): $b = 3.0$ and I uncertain with nominal value $I^* = 2.2$ fixed as left end value and support of the uniform distribution having size $\Delta I_{\max} = 0.2$. Regime (C): $I = 2.4$ and b uncertain with nominal value $b^* = 2.7$ fixed as left end value and support of the uniform distribution having size $\Delta b_{\max} = 0.2$. Regime (D): $b = 2.5$ and I uncertain with nominal value $I^* = 4.0$ fixed as left end value and support of the uniform distribution having size $\Delta I_{\max} = 0.4$. (b) For regime (C), square-wave bursting, we show the reference recurrence plot, obtained for $b \sim \mathcal{U}([2.7, 2.71])$ and $I \sim \mathcal{U}([2.4, 2.41])$, along with the recurrence plots obtained for increasing uncertainty level, for which the difference metrics are computed.

In most cases, the metrics considered in Figure S8, namely Jaccard index, mutual information index and Wasserstein distance, are not even monotonic with the uncertainty level. The Jaccard index is implemented after quantising the recurrence plot values into 1024 levels; the choice of such number directly influences the Jaccard index (fewer levels increase its value and more levels decrease its value). Only mutual information for regime (C) has a distinctive drop at uncertainty level $i = 4$ that might allow detection of loss of probabilistic robustness, as can be observed by the recurrence plots in (b); however, mutual information only works in this specific case and is not informative for other regimes. Overall, the obtained results point to the lack of applicability of the employed metrics to PRA, even in the specific case of the HR model. Generalisability to a wide family of models, therefore, seems even more questionable.

Figure S9: Unsuccessful attempt to detect loss of probabilistic robustness in the HR model subject to increasing parametric uncertainty levels $i = 1, \dots, 8$, using as a metric the power spectral density (PSD) of the mean output signal $\mathbb{E}[x_1]$. We show for each uncertainty level i the PSD (top), computed with the MATLAB function `periodogram` with a rectangular window and discrete Fourier transform length equal to the signal length, and the mean output signal (bottom). The PSD does not detect any significant changes in the related time-series. We focus on regimes (C) and (D), with parameter and uncertainty settings chosen as follows. Regime (C): $I = 2.4$ and b uncertain with nominal value $b^* = 2.7$ fixed as left end value and support of the uniform distribution having size $\Delta b_{\max} = 0.2$. Regime (D): $b = 2.5$ and I uncertain with nominal value $I^* = 4.0$ fixed as left end value and support of the uniform distribution having size $\Delta I_{\max} = 0.4$.

S3 Automated blob counting for recurrence plots

Figure S10: For recurrence plots of the membrane potential x_1 generated by the HR model in different dynamical regimes, we show the maximum blob count across all threshold values (see Figure 4e in the Main Text) as a function of \mathfrak{B} , the minimum acceptable blob size (in terms of number of pixels). The blob count is normalised by dividing it by the largest value that is computed, so that the range of values on the vertical axis is $[0, 1]$. We select the value $\mathfrak{B} = 150$ (red dashed line), which we use to compute all the results in the Main Text, because at that value the maximum blob count has a consistent and constant value for all the considered dynamical regimes. The mean signals for the recurrence plots are computed with a gPC collocation surrogate model with maximum expansion order $M = 5$ and $S_C = 250$ collocation samples. For each of the different regimes, five stochastic realisations are considered with different parameter and uncertainty settings. Regime (A): $b \sim \mathcal{U}([2.7, 2.7375])$ and $I \sim \mathcal{U}([4.3, 4.375])$; $b \sim \mathcal{U}([2.9, 2.9375])$ and $I \sim \mathcal{U}([4.0, 4.075])$; $b \sim \mathcal{U}([3.1, 3.1375])$ and $I \sim \mathcal{U}([3.6, 3.675])$; $b \sim \mathcal{U}([3.3, 3.3375])$ and $I \sim \mathcal{U}([2.8, 2.875])$; $b \sim \mathcal{U}([3.3, 3.3375])$ and $I \sim \mathcal{U}([4.2, 4.275])$. Regime (B): $b \sim \mathcal{U}([3.0, 3.05])$ and $I \sim \mathcal{U}([2.2, 2.3])$; $b \sim \mathcal{U}([3.0, 3.0625])$ and $I \sim \mathcal{U}([2.4, 2.525])$; $b \sim \mathcal{U}([3.1, 3.1125])$ and $I \sim \mathcal{U}([2.4, 2.425])$; $b \sim \mathcal{U}([3.1, 3.125])$ and $I \sim \mathcal{U}([2.6, 2.65])$; $b \sim \mathcal{U}([3.12, 3.1325])$ and $I \sim \mathcal{U}([2.8, 2.825])$. Regime (C): $b \sim \mathcal{U}([2.6, 2.625])$ and $I \sim \mathcal{U}([2.4, 2.45])$; $b \sim \mathcal{U}([2.7, 2.725])$ and $I \sim \mathcal{U}([3.0, 3.05])$; $b \sim \mathcal{U}([2.8, 2.8375])$ and $I \sim \mathcal{U}([2.6, 2.675])$; $b \sim \mathcal{U}([2.55, 2.575])$ and $I \sim \mathcal{U}([2.8, 2.85])$; $b \sim \mathcal{U}([2.65, 2.6875])$ and $I \sim \mathcal{U}([3.4, 3.475])$. Regime (D): $b \sim \mathcal{U}([2.5, 2.55])$ and $I \sim \mathcal{U}([3.4, 3.5])$; $b \sim \mathcal{U}([2.5, 2.5625])$ and $I \sim \mathcal{U}([4.2, 4.325])$; $b \sim \mathcal{U}([2.51, 2.5475])$ and $I \sim \mathcal{U}([3.8, 3.875])$; $b \sim \mathcal{U}([2.52, 2.5575])$ and $I \sim \mathcal{U}([4.0, 4.075])$; $b \sim \mathcal{U}([2.55, 2.575])$ and $I \sim \mathcal{U}([4.2, 4.25])$.

Figure S11: Blob counting procedure for the recurrence plot of the mean membrane potential $\mathbb{E}[x_1]$ of the HR model with $I = 2.4$ and $b \sim \mathcal{U}([2.5, 2.525])$. The mean output signal $\mathbb{E}[x_1](t)$ (left) is computed with a gPC collocation surrogate model with maximum expansion order $M = 5$ and $S_C = 250$ collocation samples. The corresponding recurrence plot (centre) exhibits no persistent blob count if the minimum acceptable persistence is set as $\mathfrak{P} = 0.06$, as is evident from the lack of persistent blob counts in the plot showing the blob count as a function of the threshold level (right). Therefore, the resulting blob count \mathfrak{C}^* is NaN.

Figure S12: For a nominal deterministic realisation and the corresponding mean output signal obtained when the nominal parameter values are affected by a small parametric uncertainty, although recurrence patterns can be visually very similar, the corresponding blob counts can be extremely different. This observation, which highlights the substantial difference between the deterministic and the probabilistic setting, is here exemplified in the case of the HR model. For the nominal membrane potential $x_1(t)$ obtained with $b = 2.65$ and $I = 2.4$ (left) and for the mean membrane potential $\mathbb{E}[x_1(t)]$ obtained with $b \sim \mathcal{U}[2.65, 2.66]$ and $I \sim \mathcal{U}[2.4, 2.41]$ (right), we show the time series along with the corresponding recurrence plot (top), the resulting blob count as a function of the threshold level when the minimum acceptable blob size is $\mathfrak{B} = 150$ pixels (centre), and the persistence bar chart, with minimum acceptable persistence $\mathfrak{P} = 0.05$ marked by the vertical red dashed line (bottom).

S4 Construction of the probabilistic regime preservation plot

Figure S13: Distribution of blob counts, normalised with respect to the blob count obtained at the first uncertainty level (see Section 2 (d) iii in the Main Text), in 44 non-overlapping regions of the parameter space $[b_{\min}, b_{\max}] \times [I_{\min}, I_{\max}] = [2.5, 3.3] \times [2.2, 4.4]$ of the HR model, with $N = 10$ levels of uncertainty, $\Delta_{b,\max} = 0.1$, $\Delta_{I,\max} = 0.1$ and mean output signals computed through a gPC collocation surrogate model with maximum expansion order $M = 5$ and $S_C = 250$ collocation samples. The distribution of all normalised blob counts is approximately bimodal: almost half of the occurrences are close to 1 (meaning that the blob count is approximately the same as that obtained at the first uncertainty level) and almost half of the occurrences are slightly above zero (meaning that the blob count is much smaller than that obtained at the first uncertainty level). Hence, when increasing the uncertainty level, it is reasonable to set the threshold to detect loss of probabilistic robustness when observing a change of $\pm 50\%$ with respect to the blob count at the first uncertainty level. This criterion yields the red lines in the figure, which keep the two modes of the histogram well separated.

Figure S14: Example of the procedure to construct and fill a single tile R_1 in the PRP plot, with the LE approach, for the HR model with uncertain parameter vector $Z = [b, I]^\top$. Here, R_1 has size Δb_{\max} times ΔI_{\max} (the maximum uncertainty intervals of interest), while N denotes the maximum allowable uncertainty level; all these parameters are specified by the user. The construction is sequential and hierarchical. As a first step, we arrange the rectangle R_1 . (a) At the second step, we fix the lower-left corner of R_1 and progressively increase the uncertainty level. If, in the process of increasing the uncertainty level, we cover the whole R_1 without detecting a loss of regime preservation, we are done. Otherwise, we get a smaller rectangle of parametric uncertainty (the yellow rectangle on the bottom-left of (a) above), which we denote as a rectangle of level R_2 , and we save the computed blob count and the position and size of such a rectangle of type R_2 . We then set the bottom-right corner of the obtained rectangle as a new starting point, so that it becomes the bottom-left corner of a new rectangle of level R_2 (the leftmost orange rectangle in (a) above). We then proceed to increase the uncertainty level for the new rectangle as long as no loss of regime preservation is detected. The process continues until the right side of the original rectangle R_1 is reached; then, we save the maximum height H of all the type R_2 rectangles identified so far (appearing in red in (a) above). (b) We identify the areas below H that have not been tiled yet as type R_3 rectangles and we perform a single blob count on each of the type R_3 rectangles. If such blob count is different from 0 or NaN, we save the blob count computed and the position and size of the rectangle of type R_3 ; otherwise, we further partition the type R_3 rectangle in smaller type R_4 rectangles having size $\frac{\Delta b_{\max}}{N} \times \frac{\Delta I_{\max}}{N}$, corresponding to the smallest considered uncertainty level. We then perform blob counting in each of the type R_4 rectangles and save the values along with position and size of the type R_4 rectangles. (c) The procedure is reiterated starting from the leftmost point in R_1 on the H line, and continues until each region of the tile of maximum uncertainty has an associated blob count.

S5 Additional results

S5.1 Robustness of bursting at the single-neuron level

Figure S15: For the membrane potential x_1 generated by the HR model, we report (a) the bifurcation plot in the space $[b_{\min}, b_{\max}] \times [I_{\min}, I_{\max}] = [2.5, 3.3] \times [2.2, 4.4]$ from [1] (image courtesy of Springer); and (b)-(c) PRP plots in the space $[b_{\min}, b_{\max}] = [2.5, 3.3]$, obtained with the LE approach, when (b) $I = 2.75$ and (c) $I = 3.85$. In (b) and (c), the vertical red dashed lines indicate values of b for which either a significant change in blob count occurs or the maximum uncertainty limit $\Delta b_{\max} = 0.1$ is reached; $N = 10$ uncertainty levels are considered; and the mean membrane potential $\mathbb{E}[x_1](t)$ is computed via a gPC collocation surrogate model with expansion order $M = 5$ and $S_C = 250$ collocation samples. The PRP plots tile the corresponding segments (with I fixed and b varying) and provide estimates on the preservation of dynamical regimes; specifically, the blob counts identify the dynamical regimes, while the length of the segments quantifies probabilistic robustness to parametric uncertainty.

Figure S16: For the membrane potential x_1 generated by the HR model, (a) within the bifurcation plot for $b \in [2.5, 3.3]$ and $I \in [2.2, 4.4]$ from [1] (image courtesy of Springer), we focus on the smaller parameter space $[b_{\min}, b_{\max}] \times [I_{\min}, I_{\max}] = [2.58, 2.7] \times [4.2, 4.4]$. In that parameter space, we compute (b) the PRP plot with the FG approach, on a grid of 20×10 equidistant points, with $\Delta b_{\max} = 0.1$ and $\Delta I_{\max} = 0.2$, and $N = 8$ uncertainty levels; the mean membrane potential $\mathbb{E}[x_1]$ is computed via a gPC collocation surrogate model with maximum expansion order $M = 5$ and $S_C = 250$ collocation samples. The PRP plot captures remarkably well the “palm-tree-leaf-like” shape of the burgundy area in the bifurcation plot (a), associated with the chaotic regime.

S5.2 Robustness at the cortical column level

Figure S17: For the EEG-like signal $x_2 - x_3$ generated by the JR model, we show PRP plots computed, with the LE approach, in the parameter space $[A_{\min}, A_{\max}] \times [B_{\min}, B_{\max}] = [2, 12] \times [15, 31]$, for different values of the input $p \in \{100, 200, 300, 400\}$ and the connectivity constant $C \in \{100, 125, 135, 150, 175, 190\}$, with $\Delta A_{\max} = 2$ and $\Delta B_{\max} = 2$, and $N = 8$ uncertainty levels. The mean signal $\mathbb{E}[x_2 - x_3](t)$ is computed via a gPC collocation surrogate model with maximum expansion order $M = 5$ and $S_C = 250$ collocation samples. Recurrence patterns obtained only due to numerical fluctuations are detected by checking whether, at the first uncertainty level, the difference between the maximum and the minimum of $\mathbb{E}[x_2 - x_3](t)$ is less than 10^{-7} ; whenever this is the case, a special blob count (white region) is assigned. Our numerical results demonstrate the existence of a richness of regimes in the JR model, as well as their robustness to parametric uncertainty.

Figure S18: For the EEG-like signal $x_2 - x_3$ generated by the JR model, we show PRP plots computed with the FG approach, on a grid of 20×20 equidistant points of the parameter space $[A_{\min}, A_{\max}] \times [B_{\min}, B_{\max}] = [2, 12] \times [15, 31]$, for different values of the input $p \in \{100, 200, 300, 400\}$ and the connectivity constant $C \in \{100, 125, 135, 150, 175, 190\}$. All the adopted settings and criteria are the same as in Figure S17.

References

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